

Quantum Ideas In $F=dp/dt$ and a Changing Index of Refraction?

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A photon has an energy which experimentally increases the temperature of a gas which absorbs it. This temperature may be measured by a thermometer. The point we wish to make is that there is no notion of spacetime present in this experimentally obtained idea of energy. This seems curious because according to quantum mechanics, there is an uncertainty in interaction time given by \hbar/E and so energy and uncertainty in time are linked.

One may perhaps start to see a link between E, p and x, t through the special relativistic 4-vector (pc, E) . In such a case, p and E don't exist alone, but c =speed of light of a photon in a vacuum is present. For a photon, furthermore, one has $E=pc$ and again E, p are linked to c and hence x/t . These ideas, however, do not imply quantum mechanics and resolutions in time and space linked to \hbar/E and \hbar/p . We note that special relativity is traditionally linked to Newtonian mechanics, but is an extension of this theory.

We consider the one dimensional case of a photon moving from a vacuum into a region with an index of refraction of n_2 . According to traditional ideas, the energy of the photon does not change, but $c_2=c/n_2 < c$ and $p_2= p \cdot n_2$, i.e. momentum increases. Physically, one might consider the n_2 region to contain atoms or molecules with which the photon may interact (without losing energy), but leading to time delays. In such a case, more time than expected by c would be required for a photon to travel a distance x_1 . This leads to $c_2 < c$ and energy remaining the same. At first, one might expect that momentum remains the same as well (at least in the regions between interactions with molecules/atoms). This, however, is not the case.

We suggest that if one considers the ideas of E and p being associated with Newton's second law, i.e. $dp/dt = F$. As a result, one might expect F (force) to remain the same for a photon in n_2 because when it is not interacting it is a vacuum photon. The problem is that dt must be much larger than the vacuum result, because time is wasted for interactions (and no motion occurs for these). For a fixed F , dt is larger in n_2 and so dp must be larger. If $dp = 2p$, then p must be larger as well. In fact, for $c_2=c/n = dx/dt$, where dx is fixed, $dt= dx \cdot n/c$. Then, p must change to $p \cdot n$. This, however, is still not quantum mechanical. This is known in classical physics (i.e. the Snell's law case). One may, however, examine the new resolution of $p \cdot n$. In the vacuum, one has p and a t means $x=ct$. In n_2 , t means $x= ct/n$, i.e. a reduction in resolution length by $1/n$. Now $p_2=p \cdot n$ so resolution in n_2 is given by $\text{constant}/p_2$ which is a quantum mechanical result. If one considers the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px=0$ for a photon, then using $\text{constant}/p$ for a Δx , implies $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$.

E,p and Spacetime

In Newtonian mechanics applied to a particle with rest mass, the notion of spacetime appears because:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{kinetic energy} = \int F \cdot dr \quad ((1b))$$

One, however, thinks of kinetic energy being interchanged with potential energy and momentum changes with impulse hits, rather than associating E, p with spacetime. In particular, if there is friction, a certain kinetic energy can be dissipated into heat and this heat amount equals the original kinetic energy and does not seem to be linked to spacetime. The same argument seems to apply to a photon as well because it has energy and may be absorbed in a gas to raise the temperature. This energy then does not seem to have anything to do with spacetime.

In quantum mechanics, however, a given energy E is linked with a Δt , i.e.

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((2a))$$

Index of Refraction $n_2 > n_1$ where $n_1=1$

We try to understand the idea of quantum resolution

$$((2a)) \text{ and } \Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((2b))$$

by classically examining refraction from $n_1=1$ to $n_2 > n_1$ (index of refraction).

It seems that one traditionally argues that the photon retains its energy E , while:

$$c_2 = c/n_2 < c \quad \text{and} \quad p_2 = p * n_2 > p \quad ((3))$$

These ideas are used in classical derivations of Snell's law using Fermat's Least Time Principle. They are not overtly quantum mechanical and do not implicitly imply resolutions in spacetime linked with E and p .

We suggest, however, that one may see a clear change in spatial resolution in the following manner. Traditionally, one considers that $c_2 < c$ means that a photon traveling with c in a vacuum, interacts with various atoms/molecules in n_2 . It does not lose energy, but slows down due to the fact that time is wasted in these interactions because there is no x travel. As a result, in the vacuum:

$$X = ct \quad \text{while in } n_2 \quad X = c/n_2 * t * n_2 \quad ((4))$$

In other words, a larger time $= t * n_2$ is required in n_2 to achieve the same distance. This then leads to $c_2 < c$.

We try to apply these ideas to $F = dp/dt$ ((5)).

If $dt = n * \text{usual } dt$, because of wasted time in which F is not acting, then $dp = 2p$ is also larger by n . This yields ((3)), but there is still no quantum mechanical resolution.

One may, however, see from ((4)), that if a time T represents x in $n_1=1$ (vacuum), then T represent x/n_2 in n_2 or

$$\text{constant}/p_2 \quad ((6))$$

As a result, p_2 is linked with a smaller resolution length in n_2 because $p_2 > p$. This, we argue, is a quantum mechanical idea which appears in a directly classical manner.

Using the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px = 0$ (for a photon) ((7))

one sees that $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ implies that $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. This suggests that even though a photon energy seems to produce heat, with no spacetime implications, there is actually a time implication given by \hbar/E .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that by considering a photon moving from an $n_1=1$ to an n_2 (index of refraction) region, time delays appear due to interactions with atoms/molecules in n_2 . This is like wasted time in terms of x motion. As a result, a larger time is required in n_2 for an interaction in space because some of the time is wasted due to interactions with the molecules. If one wishes Force in $F = dp/dt$ to remain the same, a larger dt implies a larger dp , by the same factor. For a fixed dx in both n_1 and n_2 , $dt = dx \cdot n/c$ so $dp = 2p$ means $p \rightarrow p \cdot n$. If one considers instead the same time T , then $x = cT$ in n_1 and $x_2 = c/nT$ in n_2 , so there is a much smaller spatial distance or resolution and this is equivalent to \hbar/p_2 where $p_2 = n \cdot p$. Thus, we argue that one may begin to see quantum mechanical ideas emerge classical through a photon moving from $n_1=1$ to n_2 .